

**DETERMINATION OF MICROORGANISMS
MARKERS BY THE METHOD GC-MS AND EFFICACY EVALUATION
of RHINOSINUSITIS**

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ABSTRACT: The work is devoted to determination of microorganisms markers by the method GC-MS (gas chromatography with ions mass detection) and efficacy evaluation of rhinosinusitis treatment. The microorganisms markers were revealed by the method GC-MS from nasal cavity, and, there were detected such microorganisms as: Streptococcus pneumoniae, Haemophilus influenzae Staphylococcus aureus, Streptococcus th viridans. β Streptococcus sanguinis, Staphylococcus sapr-hemolytic streptococcus group A, Streptococcus mitis/oralis, ophyticus, Staphylococcus epidermidis, Streptococcus haemolyticus Gram (-) flora were typical for

children of yearly age with acute rhinosinusitis which served as diagnostic criterion. Use of anise ethereal oil as antimicrobial, antiviral, antioxidant medicine led to restore microbial view in patients with acute rhinosinusitis and brought them to normal indices with efficacy 98 %.

KEYWORDS: children, early age, acute, sinusitis, ethereal oil, anise, chromatography, marker, quality, quantity, microflora.

INTRODUCTION

The problems of acute rhinosinusitis (ARS) having been urgent in connection of widespread of the given disease. Rhinosinusitis became one of the prevalent diagnoses in ambulatory practice. The statistics shows that in the USA about 15% adult populations suffer from various forms of rhinosinusitis [1], as well as in Russia approximately 10 million people suffer from this disease yearly, and, the given pathology composes from 15 to 36% [2] in structure of ENT-hospitals. According to medical statistics of Healthcare Department of Moscow City the prevalence of sinusitis makes up 1 420 cases per 100 thousand of adult population [3].

The aim of study was kind identification of microorganisms at children of early age with acute rhinosinusitis by the gas chromate-mass-spectrometry and efficacy evaluation of use ethereal oil of anise at patients treatment.

MATERIAL AND METHODS OF STUDY

The research was carried out in clinic of TashPMI (Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute). The study included 46 sick children.

As the materials were: use washings off from nasal cavity. It was carried out in aseptic conditions. 46 samples of complex analyses were taken from nasal cavities by the method GC-MS.

The components identification was carried out on the comparison base of taken mass spectrum with the library NIST and by the time keeping. The quantitative analysis was performed by the inner normalization and with the methods [35]. Statistical processing of data was carried out by application of package programs Statistica6.0.

TAKEN RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION

On the base of results analyses on markers detection there were revealed the most characteristic microorganisms in children of wasarly age with acute rhinosinusitis. The results are given in table 1. As it is seen from the table there were revealed such microorganisms as: Streptococcus pneumoniae, Haemophilus influenzae Staphylococcus aureus, Streptococcus viridans, β -hemolytic streptococcus of group A, Streptococcus mitis/oralis, Streptococcus sanguinis, Staphylococcus saprophyticus, Staphylococcus epidermidis, Streptococcus haemolyticus. Gram (-) flora disappear from microbial landscape. For normalization of microbial view, the children of early age with acute rhinosinusitis were administered the ethereal oil of anise, having exuded from the ground part of plant (The chemical content of ethereal oil of anise [36] were shown in table 2). The ethereal anise oil was prescribed children as inhalation. For this the inhalator "Micro-life" was suggested. The treatment length was from 5 to 7 days. After treatment they were undergone to secondary control analysis with GC-MS method on detection

quantitative microorganisms markers. The results were also given in table 1.

CONCLUSIONS

There were revealed the microorganisms markers by the method of gas and chromate-mass spectrometry from the nasal cavity at children of early age with acute rhinosinusitis.

The most sharply change is characteristically for the next microorganisms: Streptococcus pneumoniae, Haemophilus influenzae Staphylococcus aureus, Streptococcus viridans. β -hemolytic streptococcus of group A, Streptococcus mitis/oralis, Streptococcus sanguinis, Staphylococcus saprophyticus, Staphylococcus epidermidis, Streptococcus haemolyticus which describe the microbial view at children of early age with acute rhinosinusitis.

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Use of ethereal anise oil led to restoration of microbial view in nasal cavity and normalization of clinical picture at patient with efficacy 98 %.

